
Impact of Using Games on Enhancing Communication Skills

Dr. Osama Mohammed Ahmed Mohammed, Anwer Mohammed Elhassan Hussein,

Dr. Mohammed Elsadig Hydar Elsheikh, Safa G Omer

Jazan University - English Language Institute

osamazalama55@gmail.com, anwermohamad@gmail.com, md.elsadig21@gmail.com,

safagahalla@gmail.com

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to investigate the impact of using games in connection with the improvement of communication skills for Jazan University students to come up with appropriate solution and proposesome techniques and strategies that can enhance communication skills. Consequently, researchers have designed a questionnaire for data collection. The subject of this study is (50 ELT teachers. The (S.P.S.S) program will be used for analyzing data and interpreting the results of the study. Using games is expected to be as one of the best effective strategies for enhancing communication skills among Jazan University students. The study will answer the questions that show the relation between using games and improvement of communication skills.

Keywords: using game, communication skills

Introduction:

Communication skills are needed to speak appropriately with a wide variety of people maintaining good eye contact, demonstrate a varied vocabulary, listen effectively, present your ideas appropriately,

write clearly and concisely, and work well in a group Communication skills involve listening, speaking, and observing.

Speaking is one of the basic language skills that have to be mastered by English foreign learners due to its significance and its use for communication. It is very important to be able to speak English regarding it is the most commonly occupied language In the world so it will be very beneficial for those who comprehended it to improve their knowledge skills and get jobs. More than that, they will find it easy to communicate and interact with people around the world when they are frauds.

However, in some countries in the middle east in which English is taught as a foreign language, learners are often afraid of making mistakes and being reticulated in front of their classmates. Besides that, they may also respond in short phrases because they may not feel confident or they are too shy to speak it out.

What are communicative games?

A communicative game is a set of well fun-design activities that can stimulate students' interaction in the classroom. These games require them to take part actively in the classroom by speaking and writing to express their point of view or give information. So, one of the benefits gained

from this study is that English teachers can improve the teaching process by implementing games in English classes as a technique to enhance learners' communication skills.

Statement of the problem

Many researchers around the world have been eager to know the best method that helps students to enhance their communication skills, and most of them directed their attention to using games as one of the most effective strategies for both improving speaking abilities and making learning a foreign language easy and enjoyable.

It comes to the knowledge that few learners are aware of the impact of the use of games on their speaking capacities and the majority of teachers do not use any kind of games to improve speaking skills. Therefore, the lack of using games make the majority of the students not motivated in the English class and this for sure harms their learning process.

Objectives

- 1.To enhance the level of the students in communication skills.
- 2.To investigate the problems that Jazan University students face in communication skills.
- 3.To propose effective strategies that help students in communication.

Questions

- 1.To what extent that using games can enhance communication Skills?
- 2.What are the suitable strategies that can help the students to communicate well?
- 3.What are the problems that Jazan University students face while communicating in class?

Hypotheses

- 1.Using games is one of the best strategies that enhance communication skills.
- 2.Games are one of the most effective strategies in improving communication skills.
- 3.Games can help students to encounter shyness and building confidence.

Significance of the study

There searchers expect that this study will provide contributions in English language teaching quality when choosing games as strategy to enhance learners' communication skill.

One of the most benefits gained from this study that English teachers can improve the teaching process by implementing games in English classes as a technique to enhance learners' communication skill.

Students are expected to overcome their communication problems and get better learning which they will be able to improve their ability to practice correct grammar, vocabulary and pronounce English words properly. Students are expected also to have better speaking fluency and have great desire answering teachers' questions orally and they will have a good chance to practice English without shyness or stress, then they will like English and learn it with enjoyment.

Methodology:

This study will be conducted at Jazan University. Questionnaire has been designed for 50 ELT teachers to answer the research question, conform the hypothesis and validity of the paper. Statics package for social science program will be used for data analysis in order to find result of the questionnaire items of the research.

Limitation of the study

This paper will be limited to find out the impact of games on enhancing communication skill. Teachers and students at Jazan University will get benefit from this study.

Literature Review

Using games is one of the most effective methods to keep away from the weaknesses of the traditional English teaching method in developing students' communicative ability.

In this paper researchers applied playful games to motivate the English learning and develop oral expression. Games allows involving the students and espouses them to the use of the language, creating in them a need for communicative interaction.

Communicative games help the students to be able to practice their speaking because it usually runs in pairs or groups. Therefore, each student should have an opportunity so as to get and give information that they need.

Communicative games can help the students to become more confident to speak English because they do not feel that they are in the teaching and learning process and made a mistake without having feeling of failure. Using communicative games in the process of language teaching - learning could help all students to feel comfortable and more confident in acquiring a new language. Dr. Abdelrazig I.(2017)

When the students play communicative games, they feel enthusiastic and motivated enough to join whatever activities given to them. It means that games

can help the students to reduce their stressful and anxiety in language learning. F.Arismayang.(2016)

What is a communication problem?

There are many characteristics of communication problems that make them difficult to diagnose. Communication problems occurred if people were not able to effectively understand or convey messages being sent to them. In addition to some other problems can stem from the lack of motivation, lack of information and knowledge, not understanding cultural differences and shyness. People often blame the Arabic language for problems they are having with others or their misunderstanding, when in reality, it is the people who are making the problems happens, not the language. However, language is not the source of the lack of communication, it is the people who use and interpret language who cause this problem (Karataş, 2008).

Speaking is considered to be an important factor in the learning of a language by Shteiwi and Hamuda (2016). One of the four language skills is to speak and listen, read and write. Speaking skills are important because they represent someone's knowledge about the languages they know. According to Davies and Pearse (2000), Shteiwi and Hamuda (2016), the main objective of all English language teaching should be to enable learners to use English effectively and accurately in communication. Only the use of appropriate teaching methods as well as oral skills can achieve this.

One of the aims of the study is to investigate the problems that Jazan University students face in communication skills. The researchers have found that there

are many difficulties faced by Jazan University students in speaking English such as fear of making mistakes, fear of being laughed by their colleagues. Additionally, because they lack vocabulary, they feel scared to voice their ideas and lack the confidence to do so. Students then become less capable of speaking or become lazy as a result of these issues.

In the area of English language learning, Communication Games may be used to break down difficulties encountered by students. In fact, they're capable of improving their speaking skills.

The classroom games are more than just a fun addition to the lesson plan: they may also help teachers build closer relationships with students in order to develop skills necessary for teaching. To allow you to create activities that suit your curriculum and students' level, a number of classroom games may be modified for the purpose of introducing them. We'll be talking about classroom games and the advantages of them, taking a look at 4 curricula you should consider for your class.

1. Blindfold Game

A series of challenges can be created for everyday items inside the classroom. Students can be divided into two groups. One student should be blindfolded while the other students choose how to follow the instructions to navigate through the course in blindfold. Each group can set time to decide which communication pattern was much better in terms of effectiveness. Moreover, trust-building activity and accurate communication are needed to follow a planned course successfully. Furthermore, one student is required near the blindfolded

student to help during the course when needed.

2. True/False Storytelling

This speaking activity is very effective for enhancing communication skill. Teachers don't need any materials for this activity, just an invented story that the teacher is going to tell.

The teacher tells the students an interesting story about himself or any other invented story, then describes the details what happened. At the end of the story, the teacher gives the students an opportunity to ask questions about the story. Finally, the teacher asks the students to decide whether the story is true or false.

This activity can help students to overcome their communication problems by giving them a chance to say their opinion freely without any fear of committing a mistake.

1. Taboo Game

This is a great classroom exercise for the ESL class. This is a lot of fun, sometimes with students shouting their answers and guessing at each other they can get pretty loud.

It won't take much effort to prepare for this game, it's all very simple. At the bottom of this page, you only need to print and cut out one or more of the free printable taboo game cards. Maybe in your class you're going to explain what the word taboo means, but it doesn't really matter.

Notice that they're not permitted to speak a part of the word, an individual letter or so on. It is better to divide the class into teams. One student should come out and start the game. A student must select a card, explaining the word without having to use any forbidden words. A point shall be

awarded to the first team that comes up with a correct answer. Finally, the next student needs to come forward and do it again.

By playing the Taboo game students get to practice speaking, listening and constructing sentences. Besides, the Taboo game is helping students improve their competition, cooperation, excitement and motivation to learn vocabulary.

Spot the Difference Games

As the title suggests, players must find a specific number of differences between two images to complete this task. In order to respond, players can click in various locations throughout the images. In the spot the contrast exercise, you must identify several differences between two similar images.

It is possible that Spot the Differences is a popular and beneficial game that people of all ages like playing. It advances visual awareness, focus, comparison, and skill checking in an enjoyable manner.

Communication skills

Many scholars like (Blanka, Lidia.et al, Suwarsih, Joana, A&, James, Dewi) song game; others have stated that communication is an essential part of everyday life and it can be developed by using different techniques. Among these techniques, one is English games. In this regard, (cf. Harmer, 200) explained that learning a language is a very complicated process, so teachers need to use different strategies to address such problems. Moreover, (Caillois, 1957) argues that “a game is an activity with different characteristics such as fun, separate, uncertain, and non-productive which is

governed by rules”. On the other hand, (Hadfield, 1998) elaborated that language games can be divided into two aspects; (1) linguistic games that focus on accuracy, (2) communicative games that focus on the successful exchange of information.

Types of games

Researchers have different concepts for using games in communication (Caillois, 1957), (Tuan and Doan, 2019). Furthermore, (Zhu, 2012) has classified games into four components.

1. **Time:** Instructors should set proper time for games to be implemented as part of the content.
2. **Options:** Based on the level of the students, teachers should decide and choose appropriate types of games to be applied in the classroom considering time, purpose and interest of the students.
3. **Preparation:** When teachers prepare the games well, it will be fun.
4. **Management:** Teachers should manage the students by grouping, supervising and motivating them while they are performing their activities. Finally, teachers should keep on swapping the games for the students so that they do not feel bored.

Methodology

Participants

The sample of the study was chosen from male and female English language teachers in the English Language Institute at Jazan University. A questionnaire was

distributed to 50 ELI teachers to answer the research questions and confirm the hypothesis and reliability and validity of the study.

Instrument

A paper-based questionnaire composed of 15 questions (items) with 5-point Likert scales (1 strongly agree, agree, neutral, and strongly disagree) to collect

data.

Procedure

An analytic descriptive approach was used to analyze the data. The SPSS program was used for data analysis. The questionnaire was distributed to the participants during the academic year 2023-2024. The below tables show the details:

Table 1: Using games to enhance communication skills.

No	SA	A	N	D	SD	Mean	St.	percentage
1	21	24	4	1	0	4.3	11.5542	90%
2	13	28	7	2	0	4.04	11.2472	82%
3	29	17	4	0	0	4.5	12.7083	92%
4	25	20	4	1	0	4.38	11.6404	90%
5	14	29	5	2	0	4.1	11.8954	72%

Table 1

It is noticed from Table (1) that item 3 (Classroom activities is one of the most essential tools in enhancing communication skills) came in the highest average with a mean 4.5 and standard deviation 12.7 while the second item (Enhancing communication skills depend on extra curricula activities like games) came in the lowest average with a

mean of 4.04 and standard deviation of 11.2. (Items 1 and 5) show nearly similar means 4.1 and 4.3. Item 4 clearly shows (90 %) of the teachers agreed that using games can motivate students to communicate easily. This is the answer for the first question (To what extent that using games can enhance communication skills?)

Table 2: What are the suitable strategies that can help the students to communicate well?

No	SA	A	N	D	SD	Mean	St.	Percentage
1	33	16	1	0	0	4.64	14.543	98%
2	16	29	4	1	0	4.2	12.3895	90%
3	16	25	6	3	0	4.08	10.3199	82%
4	14	26	7	2	1	4	10.3199	80%
5	18	24	6	1	0	4.12	10.6864	84%

Table 2

It is noticed from Table (2) that overall items mean is between (4 to 4.6), which is considered (agree) with mean (4.64), and the

weighed mean for this domain tends to (agree). So, this is the answer for the second question (What are the suitable strategies that can help the students to communicate well?).

Table 3: What are the problems that Jazan University students face while communicating in class?

No	SA	A	N	D	SD	Mean	St.	Percentage
1	16	15	12	5	1	3.74	6.53452	62%
2	21	24	3	2	0	4.28	11.5109	90%
3	27	21	1	0	0	4.44	13.1415	69%
4	29	18	3	0	0	4.52	12.9808	94%
5	22	16	9	3	0	4.14	9.08295	54%

Table 3

Table 3 shows the answer for the third question (What are the problems that Jazan University students face while communicating in class?). From which the highest average was given to item 4 (Teachers should allocate sufficient time to students to Practice communicative skills.) With mean 4.52 and standard deviation 12.9. While the lowest average was given to the first item (Jazan University students usually face problems in communication with others properly and skillfully) with mean 3.7 and standard deviation 6.5.

Discussion

In the light of the data that has been collected elaborate discussion of the results in which several findings have been highlighted under each of the three premises that the paper has set, further discussions of the findings are conducted, and conclusions are drawn. The total findings of each figure are discussed as follows.

Students' communication deficiency is a problem that cannot be neglected at all. Researchers have gone through this problem and suggested using games as one of the solutions that can enhance students' communication. The survey that has been distributed among teachers in the English Language Institute at Jazan University came out with results. Most of the ELI teachers agree that classroom activities are one of the most essential tools in enhancing

communication skills. This reflects the importance of classroom activities, where we have the teacher as a moderator and students centralize the activity, managing their class activity and communicating with each other. At this stage, most of the students' fear, nervousness, and shyness vanish and are replaced by a soul of courage that gives them a chance of trial and error. ELI teachers consider games as the best strategic classroom activity for enhancing communication skills that motivate students to communicate easily and freely. Using games is one of the most effective methods that improve students' English language. Unlike traditional methods of teaching, games can develop students' communication skills through practicing English Language skills and sub-skill in a very stimulating way. ELI teachers believe that communicative games can help students to overcome communication skill problems. Teachers can address students' communication problems implicitly through communicative games. So, ELI teachers agree that using games is one of the best strategies for enhancing students' communication skills. The response to the second part of the teacher's questionnaire reflects ELI teachers' agreement with the hypothesis games are one of the most effective strategies for improving communication skills.

ELi teachers reflected that Jazan University students face problems in communication skills on different levels. 90% of ELi teachers think one of the several factors that affect students' communication skill improvement is overcrowded classrooms which demotivate the students to communicate effectively. In overcrowded classes, teachers cannot address all students and their individual needs, and demotivate students cannot find any chance to practice their communication skills break their shyness, and fears and build confidence. To overcome this problem most ELi teachers agree they should give students effective time to practice communication skills. As long as they are practicing their communication skills improve and they can defeat most of their language problems. Lack of practice is the main issue those students while communicating in English.

Conclusion

This paper aims to investigate the impact of using games in enhancing communication skills among Jazan University students. The finding indicated that this paper suggested tremendous techniques to improve student communication skills; ELi teachers agree that they should use different techniques. Variation in using different strategies and techniques gives the teacher a chance to know what is best for improving students' communication skills. Also, it makes teachers avoid redundancy which leads students to feel bored. ELi teachers believe that game competitions can also enhance students' communication skills naturally. During games students are going to focus on winning more than expected Language mistakes, Students will try to communicate in the English Language breaking lots of

psychological barriers. As we know, to improve communication skills students need to practice more and more, and games make them practice under the cover of competition and entertainment. During practicing, games can improve the cognitive ability of the students in communication skills. As they are communicating in English, either by looking for suitable words to express themselves or by listening to their colleagues' students' vocabulary will be enriched along with their sentence structure and other skills. Although students' fluency improves, they need a teacher as a moderator to guide them during this journey. ELi teachers know that using games to improve communication skills should not be ignored. Finally, as the significant impact of using games on enhancing students' communication skills is obvious, it drags students' motivation and courage to communicate through the English Language freely and easily. It leads us to the point that using games is a very effective tool that helps students to enhance their communication skills.

Teacher's Questionnaire

Dear colleagues

You are invited to participate in this study by filling out the following questionnaire. Your participation in completing that questionnaire is appreciated. Hence, there are five option to do so: strongly agree (SA), Agree (A), Neutral (N), Disagree (D) and strongly disagree (SD). Kindly tick one option.

1. Using games is the best strategic for enhancing communication skills.
2. Enhancing communications skill depend on extracurricular activity.

3. Class room activities one of the most important tools in enhance the communication skill.
4. Using games can motivate students to communicate easily.
5. Using games can help students to overcome communication skill problems.
6. Teachers should use different technique to improve students' communications skill.
7. Using games can improve the cognitive ability of the students in communication skill.
8. Should not ignore the using games to improve the communication skill.
9. Using games is very effective tools that help's students enhance communication skill.
10. Games competition can also enhance students' communication skill naturally.
11. JU students face problem in communication skill.
12. Overcrowded class rooms demotivate the students to communicate effectively.
13. Lack of practice is the main issue that encounter students while communicating in English.
14. Teachers should give students effective time to practices communication skill.
15. Communicating in English is great concern for JU students.

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